

VOCABULARY OF THE THEMATIC GROUP "FAMILY" IN THE PROVERB AND SAYINGS OF THE RUSSIAN PEOPLE.

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Annotation: The purpose of this work is to compare proverbs with the concept of "family" in the modern Russian language. The institution of the family in the traditional sense is of great importance for the whole people, and this is reflected in the proverbs of different languages. The author divided proverbs that reveal family relationships into three groups. Each of these groups was also divided into several subgroups. The purpose of this work is to compare proverbs with the concept of "family" in the modern Russian language. The institution of the family in the traditional sense is of great importance for the whole people, and this is reflected in the proverbs of different languages. The author divided proverbs that reveal family relationships into three groups. Each of these groups was also divided into several subgroups. Keywords: Proverbs, sayings, customary law, family folklore, lexical analysis, thematic groups, Russian language.

A proverb is a short phrase that embodies the deepest meaning, the experience of generations and the wisdom of the entire nation. Each proverb teaches a person, gives advice, recommends a plan of further action. This genre is very interesting for children, the words tell them a lot of new, informative, topics for reflection. In good children's proverbs, the child learns moral and ethical standards. At the end of the article, you will find famous Russian family proverbs for children, among which you are sure that they will suit your child. Good proverbs do not become relics of the past. If they talk about past affairs, then the description of the situation is done from the point of view of the present, taking into account the influence of the past on the current situation and the fruits that will appear in the near or distant future. There is a comparison of ideals and worldviews for the past and the present. Wise Russian proverbs about the family are characterized by worldly understanding and understanding of the importance of maintaining a strong and friendly family with peace and harmony at home. Every proverb expresses an opinion about what is happening, there is a proverb for every life situation. They remember themselves. These phrases educate all of us, regardless of age, the educational effect was noticed by the sages in ancient times. Here are some popular sayings about family for sighted children. What is a treasure, if the family is united. Love and advice - so there is no sorrow. Consent in the family - well-being at home, discord in the family - everything is lost. If there is only one roof, the family will be strong. A good family adds intelligence. His family doesn't have a lot of bills. The whole family is together, and the spirit is in place. In the local family and the mash is thicker. Food is tastier at the common family table. Proverbs and sayings about the family - the society in which we find ourselves from the moment of birth - play an important role in the path of life. With the support of family members, a person begins to know the world, forms his character, achieves his first goals, learns to walk, talk, behave, understands the unconditional love and loyalty of relatives. In the

family, a lot of attention is paid to the baby, which is very necessary for him in the period of the first discoveries that await the child at every step. If the situation in the family is positive, comfortable, a person can develop properly, believe in himself and his actions, which will undoubtedly help him in the next life. A good family cannot be replaced by a child, relatives are necessary people for everyone, even for adults. Russian proverbs emphasize the authority of the mother in the family, her important role in creating and maintaining the family hearth, the manifestation of care and love for her children and husband. A mother is a dear person who loves her child endlessly, regardless of his actions, other people's opinions, health. The most important authority of the child is his parents. Children want to be like them, they see their behavior and actions as the only real ones.

Working with children who learn family proverbs is often not only useful for them, but also very interesting. Parents, educators should teach the child to use folk wisdom correctly, to understand the thoughts of ancestors, to respect them, to consider them authoritative. So that this folklore genre does not pass to the next generations. Russian proverbs and sayings about the family, about the importance of preserving family values and traditions. For children and adults. Today we will focus on the recently popular family theme in Russian proverbs and sayings. A proverb is a short phrase that embodies the deepest meaning, the experience of generations and the wisdom of the entire nation. Each proverb teaches a person, gives advice, recommends a plan of further action. This genre is very interesting for children, the words tell them a lot of new, informative, topics for reflection. In good children's proverbs, the child learns moral and ethical standards. At the end of the article, you will find famous Russian family proverbs for children, among which you are sure that they will suit your child. Good proverbs do not become relics of the past. If they talk about past affairs, then the description of the situation is done from the point of view of the present, taking into account the influence of the past on the current situation and the fruits that will appear in the near or distant future. There is a comparison of ideals and worldviews for the past and the present. Wise Russian proverbs about the family are characterized by worldly understanding and understanding of the importance of maintaining a strong and friendly family with peace and harmony at home. Proverbs and sayings about the family - the society in which we find ourselves from the moment of birth - play an important role in the path of life. With the support of family members, a person begins to know the world, forms his character, achieves his first goals, learns to walk, talk, behave, understands the unconditional love and loyalty of relatives. In the family, a lot of attention is paid to the baby, which is very necessary for him in the period of the first discoveries that await the child at every step. If the situation in the family is positive, comfortable, a person can develop properly, believe in himself and his actions, which will undoubtedly help him in the next life. A good family cannot be replaced by a child, relatives are necessary people for everyone, even for adults. Russian proverbs emphasize the authority of the mother in the family, her important role in creating and maintaining the family hearth, the manifestation of care and love for her children and husband. A mother is a dear person who loves her child endlessly, regardless of his actions, other people's opinions, health. The most important authority of the child is his parents. Children want to be like them, they see their behavior and actions as the only real ones. Working with children who learn family proverbs is often not only useful for them, but also very interesting. Parents, educators should teach the child to use folk wisdom correctly, to understand the thoughts of ancestors, to

respect them, to consider them authoritative. So that this folklore genre does not pass to the next generations.

In the pre-state society, proverbs and sayings as a genre of folklore codified the unwritten laws of social behavior. With the formation of the state and the "law of the written word", proverbs and sayings are being pushed to the periphery of social life as customary law (legal custom), an important component of the language environment of modern man. Currently, they regulate mainly intra-family life and exist in opposition to official law. The life of a person outside the home in proverbs and sayings is dedicated to the fulfillment by a person of social duties and the rules of social, social behavior. A special place here is occupied by proverbs about the role of the word in social communication. The behavior of a person in the family circle is determined by those customs that are not recorded anywhere and obviously date back to ancient times, since they are based on the very archaic right of the strong and the right of the first. In addition to general household rules, it describes the relationship of parents with children and the relationship between spouses. The third group of proverbs and sayings formulates not the norms of behavior in them, but the laws beyond the control of man.

Proverbs are a generalization of the centuries-old life experience of the people, contain an emotionally expressive assessment of human actions, events, and phenomena. With the help of units of everyday consciousness, one can join the way of thinking of the people, come closer to comprehending the originality of the national character, the national system of values. The appeal to the concept of "family" is due to the fact that it occupies a significant place in the life of an ethnic group and, as a result, receives a rich historical and cultural content. The family has become the focus of basic life values, happiness, prosperity. And at the same time, both positive and negative character traits of family members are manifested in family relations, which determine their behavior and attitude towards each other. Family and relationships in the family are quite widely represented in the proverbs of the Russian people.

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